

Assessing Cognitive Load and Temporal Dynamics of Brain Activity During Landmark-Based Navigation Using Mobile Maps

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Studying brain activity and cognitive load during navigation with a mobile map in realistic virtual environments is a multifaceted endeavour. Cheng et al. (2023) addressed this issue by using spontaneous eye-blinks during navigation as event markers in electroencephalography (EEG) recordings. Prior research shows that eye-blink derived Event Related Potentials (bERP) are indicative of cognitive load. By analysing EEG data based on those markers during navigation in unfamiliar urban areas with a mobile map featuring 3, 5, or 7 landmarks, they identified an optimal number of landmarks for effective navigation. Building on their research methodology and experimental design, we adapted the approach to a 360-degree cylindrical projection immersive virtual environment, incorporating mobile EEG and realistic locomotion techniques.

Our study investigates cognitive load during navigation with mobile maps showing 5, 6, or 7 landmarks, aiming to determine whether cognitive load increases when six landmarks are displayed and levels off at seven, or if it continues to rise with more than five landmarks. Additionally, we are employing microstate analysis, which identifies brief intervals of stable scalp potential fields (microstates) generated by brain networks. This method provides insights into the temporal dynamics of brain activity and large-scale network functions, helping us understand cognitive processes and differences in brain activity during navigation among individuals. By combining bERP and microstate analysis, our research contributes to advancing the field of spatial cognition and navigation. This integrated approach enhances our understanding of the relationship between the number of landmarks displayed on mobile maps and cognitive load, potentially guiding the development of neuroadaptive maps, as proposed by Cheng et al. (2023). Moreover, it enables the extension of existing research on individual differences (such as cognitive ability, experience, and impairment) in navigation performance, offering valuable insights that may inform new strategies to support individuals with cognitive decline in wayfinding tasks.

References

Cheng, B., Lin, E., Wunderlich, A., Gramann, K., & Fabrikant, S. I. (2023). Using spontaneous eye blink-related brain activity to investigate cognitive load during mobile map-assisted navigation. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 17, 1024583.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2023.1024583>